

APPLICATION OF A TITANIUM – CARBON FIBRE METAL LAMINATE IN AN IN-FLIGHT OPENING FIGHTER DOOR LOADED IN ACOUSTIC FATIGUE.

PART I: DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper discusses the results of a design project with the goal to research and promote the use of Fiber Metal Laminates (FML) in other applications than currently under exploration. In view of one of the strong points of Glare[®] (an FML of glass fiber reinforced epoxy prepreg between aluminum sheets), superior fatigue properties compared to solid aluminum, an in-flight opening door of a fighter aircraft was selected to be designed in a new FML. This fighter door is subject to a high acoustic loading and operated at high temperature. This paper deals with the design and analysis of the component in an FML of titanium and a carbon fiber reinforced polymer. Also tests on material and component level are discussed.

The design of the component has been established with an ordinary design procedure: create design concepts based on the requirements, analyze their mechanical behavior, trade off the design concepts and choose the best concept for further evaluation. The best design concept was designed in detail for a full-scale acoustic fatigue test. The complex part of this project was that within the overall design process, an extra design process can be identified: the design of the FML itself. This extra design process is discussed and the results are used in the design of the fighter door.

To avoid extensive experimental studies, it was chosen to design a new FML using computational models. Three independent parameters are identified to design the FML and a parameter study is presented in which the mechanical properties of the FML are calculated. The actual choice of the two parameters is based on a finite element model in which shear and peel stresses in the interface layer between the fibers and the titanium are calculated at a crack. After the lay-up of the FML is chosen, its fatigue properties are determined by tests and compared to titanium.

The full-scale test on the door has been performed using a shaker instead of an acoustic chamber. The random mechanical load applied by the shaker generates similar running loads in the fighter door as the acoustic load. The test results are used to verify the computational results.

Introduction

In December 2000, a joint research program funded by the Netherlands Agency for Aerospace Programmes (NIVR) was started with the goal to investigate and promote the use of new Fiber Metal Laminates (FML) in other applications than currently under exploration.

A SWOT analysis of Glare[®], an FML of glass fiber reinforced epoxy prepreg between aluminum sheets [11, 12], is summarized in Figure 1. Opportunities were identified for new FML variants with strong points comparable to Glare[®] but with enhanced performance with respect to operational temperature, stiffness and deformability.

The development of new FML focused on two variants: an elevated temperature alternative for Glare[®], ET - Glare[®] with an increased operational temperature, and a high temperature FML based on titanium and carbon fibers. This HT

FML is developed for both a high operational temperature and a high stiffness. This paper deals with the development of the HT FML and of a primary structural component in this HT FML

To research the capabilities of the new HT FML, it was considered best to start a product development project and design and build a primary structural component. The requirements for this component have to justify the use of HT FML. An in-flight opening door of a fighter aircraft was selected to be designed in HT FML. This door is subject to high acoustic loads and is used at high temperature. Furthermore, the door is in a zone of the aircraft where foreign object damage (FOD) occurs.

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatigue resistance • Damage tolerance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatigue • Impact / FOD • Fire resistance • Corrosion resistance • Residual strength after fatigue • Reparability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited operational temp. • Low modulus • Limited deformability
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FML variants for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high temperature • high stiffness • 3 dimensional shapes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costly image

Figure 1 SWOT analysis of FML

This paper deals with the design and analysis of the fighter door in an FML of titanium and a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP). The door is designed for a full-scale fatigue test with random loading. The contents of the paper is subdivided into two parts. In the first part, the conceptual design of a new FML is discussed. In the second part, the design and engineering of the fighter door in HT FML for a full-scale random fatigue shaker test will be described. Also tests on material, sub-component and component level are discussed.

Conceptual design of a new FML

Before the design of the fighter door in a new HT FML could be started, the HT FML itself had to be designed. Due to its laminated nature, an FML is not a material but a structure itself. In its most general kind, the composite laminate of an FML consists of some type of sheet metal in combination with some type of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) ply. The resin in the FRP plies acts as adhesive to bond metal and FRP plies to a composite laminate with groups of FRP plies between two sheet metal plies. On forehand, the type of metal, the type of fibers and the type of polymer matrix are unknown. Next to this, also the relative thickness of the sheet metal and the FRP must be determined in combination with the orientation of the fibers and the lay-up of the FML.

To limit the number of parameters, a few preliminary choices have been made based on the requirements for the new FML. In the first place, the new HT FML must behave like Glare[®]. In the SWOT analysis, it was assumed that a strength of FML is that it has improved fatigue properties and impact properties compared to the metal used in the FML. The new HT FML must have these properties also and combine them with high temperature capabilities and high strength and stiffness at low weight to compete with full metal and full composite structures. For new material combinations, this has to be proven by tests.

In addition to the requirements, two boundary conditions have to be met. Boundary conditions are not imposed by the use of the structural part to be made in HT FML but avoid delays of the project. First, the constituents chosen for the FML must be readily available. Second, the materials had to be approved by possible end-users.

Based on the requirements and the boundary conditions, an initial choice of the constituents of the FML was made. The new FML consists of titanium Ti-6Al-4V, Carbon IM7 fibers and a cyanate ester resin (Bryte EX-1551). The titanium alloy was chosen for its good properties at high temperatures and its good fatigue properties. Availability forced the choice of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy. Titanium Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn was the preferred alloy for its higher tensile strength, its better corrosion properties and lower cost but appeared not to be available as sheet metal at the required thickness. The IM7 carbon fibers have been selected for their good strength and stiffness properties compared to the more common T300 carbon fibers. The cyanate ester resin has been chosen for its initial cure temperature of 120° C followed by a post cure cycle at 180° C to 200° C thus increasing its operating temperature to 180° C.

Two other limiting choices were made based on similarity with Glare[®]. First, the fibers in the FML will only have orientations of 0° and 90°. The in-plane shear properties of an FML are established by the sheet metal plies. Second, the

fiber reinforced plies in the FML will be applied in FML type 3 lay-up. An FML type 3 has a fiber package of 2 unidirectional fiber reinforced plies in between two sheet metal plies as listed in Table 1. Within a type of FML, the lay-up can vary from 2-1 (two sheet metal plies, one package of fiber reinforced plies) or 3-2 up to any number of sheet metal plies required. Please note that an FML 3 2-1 has an asymmetric lay-up and has anisotropic material properties on the laminate level.

	ply orientation	ply type		ply orientation	ply type
1	-	Ti-6V-4Al	1	-	Ti-6V-4Al
2	0	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester	2	0	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester
3	90	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester	3	90	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester
4	-	Ti-6V-4Al	4	-	Ti-6V-4Al
			5	90	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester
			6	0	unidirectional IM7 carbon cyanate ester
			7	-	Ti-6V-4Al

Table 1 Laminate lay-up of HT FML 3 2-1 (left) and HT FML 3 3-2 (right)

The requirements, boundary conditions and choices discussed above leave two parameters to be determined: The thickness of the titanium sheet metal plies and the thickness of the IM7 carbon fiber reinforced cyanate ester plies.

For the final design of the FML for which these two parameters will be determined, the next strategy has been used. To avoid extensive screening test programs on numerous varieties of FML, it was decided to use computational tools for the initial screening. These computational tools consist of existing software based on the classical lamination theory [6] and finite element calculations. The results of these calculations are used to facilitate choices for the thickness of the sheet metal plies and the fiber reinforced plies. Tests will be done on HT FML specimen with the lay-up as calculated to substantiate the results of the calculations.

Parameter study

The first type of calculations are based on the Classical Lamination Theory [7] embedded in a software tool [5]. For 4 different thicknesses of the titanium plies, 0.2, 0.375, 0.5 and 0.6 mm and for 6 overall thicknesses of the FML, 1.5, 2.25, 3.75, 5.25 6.75 and 8.25 mm, mechanical properties have been calculated and plotted versus the overall thickness of the FML. Each thickness of FML corresponds to a lay-up, 1.5 mm with a 2-1 lay-up, 2.25 mm with a 3-2 lay-up etc. To keep the overall thickness of the FML constant, the thickness of the fiber reinforced ply has to be tuned. The corresponding thicknesses of the fiber reinforced plies can be calculated from the “fiber volume fraction” that in this case is defined as the ratio of the volume of all fiber reinforced plies (fibers and resin) over the overall thickness of the FML. Note that this definition is different from the definition used for composites where fiber volume fraction is the ratio of the fiber volume over the volume of the composite. The volume of the composite consists of fibers and resin.

Figure 2 HT FML mechanical properties versus overall FML thickness

A number of properties calculated in [4] are plotted in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The most important conclusions drawn in [4] are:

1. The stiffness of the HT FML is between 80 GPa and 100 GPa compared to about 50 GPa for Glare[®]. The flexural stiffness for HT FML is between 85 GPa and 110 GPa compared to about 65 GPa for Glare[®].
2. For larger overall thicknesses of the FML, the distribution of the different materials is more equal over the FML. Therefore out-of-plane properties do not change much anymore for constant v_f . The lay-up has less influence on thicker laminates.
3. In case of thickness constraints of the FML, use titanium or stainless steel only instead of FML. The absolute properties of titanium are better than that of the CFRP plies. This would mean that the carbon fibers only weaken the titanium. But when the weight is included by calculating specific properties, then carbon fiber reinforced composites perform better. This is only valid for static properties, not for fatigue properties.
4. When thicknesses may be higher (or should be to eliminate stability problems), add carbon fiber reinforced plies to the metal for a stiffer and stronger structure at a lower weight.
5. Specific flexural stiffness increases with increasing prepreg volume contents. In general CFRP have better flexural stiffness and flexural strength per unit weight.

Next to mechanical properties, also internal thermal stresses due to cooling after curing have been calculated using [5]. These thermal stresses due to a temperature decrease of 100° C are plotted in Figure 4. The thermal stresses can be as large as 90 MPa (compressive) in the CFRP plies and 40 MPa (tensile) in the titanium plies. At temperatures below curing temperature, these internal stresses will have a negative influence on the fatigue performance of the HT FML. At temperatures above curing temperature, the titanium is loaded in compression which might postpone the initialization and growth of fatigue cracks. It is important to realize the presence of the internal thermal stresses for FML types with an asymmetric lay-up (like HT FML 3 2-1). These FML might warp after production due to the thermal stresses.

Figure 3 HT FML specific mechanical properties versus overall FML thickness

Figure 4 HT FML internal thermal stresses

Shear stresses at a crack tip

The parameter study discussed above only gave a general overview of the mechanical and physical properties of the HT FML. The fatigue related properties of the combination of titanium with carbon fiber reinforced plies were still unknown. To determine an optimum for the relative thicknesses of the different plies in the HT FML and to substantiate that the HT FML could perform in fatigue equal to Glare[®], a finite element model was developed.

The outstanding fatigue properties of Glare[®] are established by the combination of fibers, metal and resin [11, 12]. Although the resin has inferior mechanical properties compared to the other two constituents, it plays an important role in the fatigue behavior. At the tip of a crack in an FML, the resin is the only component that can transfer stresses from

the cracking metal to the crack-bridging fibers. For the new HT FML to have similar capabilities to that of Glare[®], it was assumed that the shear and peel stresses in the resin at a crack tip in the new HT FML must be comparable to or lower than the stresses found in Glare[®]. If this is the case the new FML could behave like Glare[®]. In Glare[®], controlled delamination occurs. This is a phenomenon between two extremes. When no delamination takes place, the fiber will break. When too much delamination takes place then crack bridging would not take place.

In a finite element model discussed in [8], a cross section somewhere at the cracked plate was simulated with a mesh depicted in Figure 5. It is very difficult to calculate the absolute quantity of peel and shear stresses at the crack tip which was well beyond the scope of the project. But if the finite element mesh is kept constant and only the materials in the different plies are varied, then the results can be used for comparison with Glare[®]. The shear and peel stresses calculated in the resin rich layer at the crack tip are plotted in Figure 6. In the calculations, the internal thermal stresses have been included. This figure shows clearly that of all combinations, titanium - IM7 carbon fibers - cyanate ester has the lowest peel and shear stresses.

Figure 5 Geometry and finite element mesh of a crack tip [8]

Figure 6 Shear and peel stresses in various FML variants including temperature effects [8]

The final choice for the thickness of the plies in the HT FML was made from finite element calculations with this model in which the thickness of the plies was varied.

Extra FEM calculations

In view of the strategy chosen for the development of new FML (base the design of the new FML on calculations which are verified or adapted afterwards) also other finite element models have been developed for the calculation of non-linear stress - strain curves, for the blunt notch strength and for the prediction of crack growth rates. These calculations are discussed in [1, 2].

Tests on a Titanium – Carbon FML

Several test programs have been carried out. In the first place to provide material data of the CFRP plies for the FE calculations, in the second place to provide data on some input parameters for the finite element models (size and shape of the delamination area at the crack tip for crack growth rate calculations [2]), in the third place to provide design allowables (e.g. for crippling) and in the fourth place to substantiate the improved fatigue properties of the HT FML compared to titanium. The fatigue tests on HT FML are discussed in [3] and a few of the results will be reviewed here.

Constant amplitude fatigue tests were carried out on rectangular specimens of Titanium Ti-6Al-4V-annealed and of HT FML 3-2 lay-up (see Table 1) with two saw cuts of 5 mm, one at 1/3 and one at 2/3 of the specimen length. The stress ratio ($\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$) is 0.1 to prevent compressive loads on the specimens. Since no experience was available with the HT FML, a first estimate of the stress level to be applied in the fatigue test was based on titanium properties known from literature. As a first attempt, a stress amplitude of 120 MPa was chosen. During the test programs, this level has been increased to 180 MPa, 210 MPa and 240 MPa to study the crack growth rates for the HT FML as a function of the

applied stress. The results of the fatigue tests for both the titanium and the HT FML are plotted in Figure 7. At the different amplitude stress levels, the crack length in the HT FML increases linearly with the number of cycles indicating constant crack growth rates independent of the crack length. For the applied titanium, two curves are plotted at each amplitude stress level and each crack length. One curve has been derived from literature [10], the other was measured in the test. In the titanium, the crack growth rate increases with the crack length. The curves in Figure 7 show clearly that the HT FML has better fatigue properties than titanium and behaves similar to Glare®.

Figure 7 Crack growth curves of titanium and HT FML 3 3-2

Structural design of the in-flight opening fighter door

The outcome of the design of the HT FML as a laminate is that sheet metal plies of 0.2 mm (based on availability of materials) in combination with unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced cyanate ester plies with a thickness of 0.125 mm are preferred. These plies are used in the design of the fighter door in HT FML as discussed below.

At the start of the design process, no design allowables were available for the new HT FML (apart from those calculated). Therefore, it was decided to make a point design: design a component without the allowables exactly known and prove its strength by testing the single component. The design allowables used are those for the titanium and the CFRP.

Figure 8 The geometry of the fighter door

Figure 9 Open cavity acoustics spectrum

Requirements

The requirements for which the door was designed are numerous. Next to all kinds of natural and induced environmental loads, the door must meet functional requirements and is designed to carry the loads applied to it within a cost and weight target. The main functional requirements are that the inner and outer mould lines are fixed and determine the geometry of the door, see Figure 8. The door is supported by 5 hinges. Their position was free but there is

a keep-out-volume at the middle of the door. Four of the five hinges are actuated. Important detail is the dent in the middle of the door.

The goal of the project was to prove the feasibility of a heavily loaded primary structural part designed in HT FML. To achieve this goal within the time schedule of the project, it was decided to consider the most heavy load case and design the door for this case. The most severe load is assumed to be an acoustic load induced by the open cavity while the door is opened in flight. The acoustic load consists of random sound pressures in a certain frequency range. The sound pressure levels over the frequency range are plotted in Figure 9.

Design concept

Based on the requirements, several design concepts were developed of which one was chosen for further analysis. The design concept chosen is depicted in Figure 10 and consists of an outer skin and an inner skin of HT FML. In between these two skin, a corrugated core of CFRP is placed. Doublers have been placed between the corrugation and the skins to smoothen the transition of supported and unsupported skin and reduce peel stresses due to out-of-plane vibrations. Furthermore it is assumed that fatigue cracks will not occur in the doubler but in the outside titanium ply where it can be detected more easily. The skins of the door are made of HT FML and must prove the strong points and the opportunities of the application of the new HT FML as identified in the SWOT analysis: good fatigue and impact properties in combination with high stiffness and high temperature capabilities. The feasibility check on the 3D deformability for HT FML is included in the inner skin that has double curved areas at the edges and at the dent. The manufacturing and assembly of the parts of the door are discussed in [9].

Figure 10 Internal structure of the corrugated concept

The load paths in the door are as follows: The inner and the outer skin carry all acoustic loads applied to the door and distribute them to the corrugation. The corrugations are placed in length direction of the door to provide bending stiffness to the door in the unsupported area between hinge 3 and 4. Furthermore, the corrugation takes up the loads on the skin and transfers these loads as transverse shear loads to the CFRP hinge beams perpendicular to the corrugations. These hinge beams transfer all loads to the hinges that are connected to the aircraft and to the actuators.

Detail design and engineering

For the further design and engineering of the corrugated core concept design, a finite element model has been developed [13]. This FE model has been set up in MSC/Patran for use in a frequency response analysis with MSC/Nastran. The model contains all structural items required for a detailed analysis:

- The element size has been chosen such that local deformations between the corrugations can be calculated. This makes the model also suitable for local buckling analysis.
- The doublers have been modeled by choosing appropriate element sizes using double biases for the mesh seeds.
- The hinge brackets are separate parts that are connected to the door by equivalencing nodes at the position of the rivets. The use of multi point constraints (MPC's) has been avoided because they cannot be used in buckling a analysis.
- The shell elements for the skins and the corrugation have been defined with the exact laminate lay-up as in the actual door. This enables the tuning of the lay-up of the HT FML in high loaded areas. The result is that within a single product, different types and different lay-up of FML are used: HT FML 5 2-1 in both skins, HT FML 3 3-2 in the skins at the reinforcements for the hinge brackets.

Frequency response analysis

The primary goal of the finite element model was to analyze and design the fighter door for acoustic fatigue. Opposite to constant amplitude (CA) fatigue, the nature of acoustic fatigue loading is random. This means that in time the exact value for the sound pressure is unknown and can only be described by means of statistics. A typical way of representing random acoustic loads is plotted in Figure 9. Over a frequency range, the sound pressure level (SPL) is defined. The

SPL is a measure for the root mean square (RMS) sound pressure at a certain frequency. The acoustic fatigue spectrum in Figure 9 is used in a frequency response analysis in MSC/Nastran.

A frequency response analysis is subdivided in the next steps:

1. Perform a natural frequency analysis and check which eigenmodes are relevant. The first eigenmode shape and its corresponding frequency is plotted in Figure 12.
2. Run the actual frequency response analysis. In this analysis, transfer functions under unit load are calculated for each type of output result specified in the input deck (stress, strain, running load, displacement etc.) and at every frequency specified. It is important to define a sufficient number of evaluation frequencies at every natural frequency to capture the structural response correctly.
3. Once the transfer functions are known for all desired output quantities over the frequency range of interest, then the response to the actual random spectrum can be calculated in a post-process calculation. Note that a single frequency response calculation (step 2) can be used to analyze different input spectra.

Failure modes

The results of the frequency response analysis are RMS values for the requested output quantities. With these results, the margins of safety for several failure modes and at different locations in the door are calculated. On locations of insufficient strength, the design of the fighter door is modified.

The major failure mode identified is failure in acoustic fatigue. There were five problems to solve before margins of safety for this failure mode can be calculated. The first problem is that no fatigue allowables are available for the new HT FML. This problem is solved by considering the stresses in the titanium plies and use the stresses in these plies to check failure on fatigue. The second problem is that in the frequency response analysis, it appeared not possible to calculate RMS stresses and strains in the plies of the laminate of the FML. Therefore, the running loads on the laminate have been calculated and [6] is used to calculate the RMS stresses in the plies of the FML. The applied stresses now have to be compared to the allowable stresses. The third problem is that for titanium no random amplitude (RA) fatigue data are available. In [10], constant amplitude (CA) fatigue data are listed. These data have been used for RA fatigue using a reduction factor on the fatigue stress. The fourth difficulty is that CA fatigue data for titanium are not available for a stress concentration factor K_t equal to 6. The fatigue data at this K_t , that occurs in the single lap riveted joint of the hinge brackets to the FML of the inner skin, have been derived by extrapolation from the CA fatigue data for lower K_t - values in [10]. The fifth problem was the presence of thermal stresses due to cooling down after curing. The parameter study revealed that these stresses can be rather large. The full-scale test will be performed at room temperature at which the internal stresses are most unfavorable: compression in the CFRP plies and tension in the titanium plies. Therefore, a linear static analysis was performed with the FE model loaded by a temperature decrease of 100° C to calculate the thermal stresses. These stresses were considered mean stresses to which the RMS stresses due to the acoustic load have to be added as amplitude stresses. Now, the fatigue allowables for titanium cannot be derived for the stress ratio $R = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = -1$ anymore. The allowables have to be calculated for the appropriate stress ratio at each location using the correct thermal stress and the corresponding RMS stress at that location.

The approach described above is conservative due to the use of a conservative reduction factor on the CA fatigue data and due to neglecting the effect of the fibers on the fatigue behavior of the titanium. A third assumption that introduces extra conservatism is the use of a reduction factor on the fatigue life. To account for scatter in the RA fatigue properties, the service life of the door is multiplied with a factor 4.

Next to acoustic fatigue, other, quasi-static failure modes have been checked: crippling, bearing and buckling. The RMS fatigue stresses calculated are the average stresses that occur in the door. However, these stresses (and the corresponding running loads) have a statistical distribution about this average. This means that stresses up to three times the RMS stresses are likely to occur. These so-called 3σ (in which σ stands for the statistical quantity standard deviation, not for stress) are less probable to occur but can yield quasi-static failure in the failure modes mentioned. The 3σ values have been used to check the door on crippling and on bearing. To check and prevent local buckling under the acoustic load, a linear buckling analysis has been performed. The non-linear buckling load was derived the linear buckling load by use of a reduction factor of 0.5. At this estimated non-linear buckling load, the running loads at the location of buckling were higher than the RMS running loads calculated. Therefore, it is assumed that buckling will not occur in the door under the acoustic load.

Full-scale shaker test

The fighter door described in this paper has been designed for a full-scale acoustic fatigue test. To learn about the random amplitude fatigue behavior of the HT FML as much as possible, the door is designed to fail at a favorable position in acoustic fatigue. The lowest margin to failure has been predicted at the transition of the flat inner skin to the dent. Here, rivets have been used to prevent delamination of the FML. Due to the stress concentrations around the rivet holes and the relatively thin FML at this location, the largest stresses are found here.

Test set-up

To simulate the actual acoustic loading encountered in practice, it would have been best to test the door in an acoustic chamber. However, such facilities are very rare and very expensive, especially for the sound pressure levels the door is subjected to. Therefore, it was decided to do the full-scale test with a shaker, see Figure 11. The test has been set-up to simulate the responses due to the acoustic loading as good as possible. This is established as follows. An excitation point is selected at which the shaker applies its random force/displacement to the door. This position has been chosen such that the shaker can excite all important eigenmodes of the door. To be able to excite an eigenmode, the shaker force must be applied away from the nodes (points with zero translation) of the eigenmode.

Design of test spectrum

After this point has been chosen, the frequency response analysis of the door was repeated, now for a unit force over the correct frequency range (in N^2/Hz) applied at this position. Under this unit force, the response of the door (in accelerations perpendicular to the plane of the door) at the desired failure location near the dent was determined and compared with the calculated response of the door under the acoustic load and at the same location. Then the unit input force was scaled, using a 1-Hertz bandwidth, such that the response of the door at the dent under the acoustic load and under the (theoretic) shaker load were identical. This scaled shaker load applied at the point where the shaker is connected to the door will yield the same running loads in the test as found for the acoustic load.

Figure 11 Set-up of the full-scale shaker test

It appeared that the shaker could not generate the overall level of the accelerations over the complete frequency range. Therefore, the frequency range of the test was truncated at 200Hz. It was assumed that the first eigenmodes, that are all lower than 200 Hz, contribute most to the damage so that the truncation has little influence on the outcome of the test.

Results of the natural frequency tests

To validate the FE-model, modal analysis measurements were performed to determine the actual natural frequencies and mode shapes of the door. The results of the finite element calculations are very well corresponding to the measured results. A transfer function between the acceleration of the door and the shaker force is plotted in Figure 13. The first eigenmode calculated is plotted in Figure 12. Its frequency is 49.2 Hz. The transfer function of the door shows the first eigenfrequency at 55 Hz. The little shift in the first eigenfrequency might be due to differences in the hinge brackets used in the full-scale test. A more detailed comparison of the eigenfrequencies and the eigenmode shapes is discussed in [5].

Figure 12 The first eigenmode shape at 49.2 Hz.

Figure 13 Measured transfer function of the door

Results of the shaker tests

The shaker test and the results will be reported in [5]. The test article survived the test at the random load it was designed for. The determined life was far larger than the required service life. The full-scale test was stopped after a 9 % drop of the first natural frequency. Failure occurred at the connection of the shaker to the door. Nowhere in the door, failure in the HT FML was detected. The measured RMS strains have to be compared to the calculations.

Conclusions and recommendations

A complete research program has been carried out in which next to a new high temperature FML in titanium and carbon fiber reinforced cyanate ester also a primary structural component in this new HT FML has been designed. The thicknesses of the plies in the HT FML have been chosen based on a FE model in which the shear and peel stresses in the resin at the crack are compared to Glare[®]. Fatigue tests have shown that the new HT FML has superior fatigue properties compared to titanium.

The new HT FML has been used in an in-flight opening fighter door that consists of a flat HT FML outer skin, a double curved HT FML inner skin and a carbon fiber reinforced cyanate ester corrugation. The door has been designed for a full-scale acoustic fatigue test. The door passed the test and proved the capabilities of HT FML in a primary structure.

The door did not fail in the test and has probably been designed too heavy due to conservative assumptions in the estimation of the allowables. A complete screening test program should be carried out to give an indication of the properties of the HT FML in number of fields: static strength, blunt notch, crippling, compression after impact, open hole tension, constant amplitude fatigue, random fatigue etc. These tests should be used to tune and develop the computational models so that they can be used for the design of new FML dedicated to a specific application.

The high temperature capabilities have not been proven yet. The effect of internal thermal stresses must be researched further.

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